

Turning the Tide in Europe

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Europe faces economic challenges, its innovation pace is struggling to compete with global competition, and social acceptance towards and regulation for transformation is lacking. In light of this context, the European clean energy transition is in danger of being down prioritised.

Worst case scenario starting to look realistic

In 2023, the clean energy transition partnership project [Man0EUvRE](#) started research with the aim to unite energy system modellers across Europe and find solutions for how Europe, through joint undertaking, can lower the costs and increase the speed of the green shift.

The project has studied a possibility space characterised by four scenarios, the European Energy Vision scenarios [1], describing different possible futures. The scenarios have been analysed using simulations in a pan-European model ([2] and e.g., [3]) and in 9 different case studies with different geographical or sectoral scopes [4]. *GoRES* is a best-case scenario with a high pace of innovation, social acceptance of new technology and geopolitical stability. The *NECP Essentials* scenario implements the currently delivered national energy and climate plans [5] with existing measures until 2040, and a continuation of today's trends after that. The *REPowerEU++* scenario resembles the previous one, while assuming more cooperation within Europe – imitating a Europe with more cooperation to reach the

climate goals. *EU Trinity* is a worst-case scenario that includes high geopolitical instability, a slower pace of innovation, and lower social acceptance of new technology and habits. *EU Trinity* has many similarities with the situation that Europe now faces within the economy, public attitude and awareness of the transformation, innovation, geopolitical instability, and policy and regulations, which are outlined in the following sections. It must be underlined that the European Energy Vision scenarios represent long-term pathways for possible futures. This report focuses on short-term realities that have emerged since the development of the European Energy Vision Scenarios. Therefore, this report will act as a warning of possible consequences if the right measures are not taken, and to encourage policy makers to implement recommendations that steer Europe in the direction of the more ambitious possible futures.

Economy

Europe is facing a triple challenge regarding the economy, which will reduce the possibility to invest in green technologies as originally outlined in the REPowerEU [6] strategy: Support to the Ukrainian struggle for freedom requires continued civil and military support from the EU, while the security situation in general has committed NATO members to raise their defence budget to 5% of GDP. International trading is hampered by tax-wars, and especially the tax initiatives from the US administration have resulted in plans for further increase in fossil gas imports from the US. Europe is falling behind in the global competition, which puts pressure on job and wealth creation in Europe. A consequence is the observed growth in European state debt, leading to further strain on the economy [7].

Public attitude to and awareness of transformation

Societal awareness plays a significant role in people's and industry's impact on climate change mitigation. Societal acceptance is crucial for deployment rates of renewables, storage solutions and grid infrastructure [8], for policy measures, especially when having financial impact on households and industry [9]. It impacts improvements in efficiency, the strength of rebound effects, and the potential for demand-side flexibility. People's attitude does not shift frequently or quickly, and therefore, there have not been many changes since the development of the European Energy Vision scenarios. However, some factors can have a large impact on societal attitudes and behaviour, like the economy. When people have less money and faith in the future, their energy consumption behaviour is impacted. Specifically, energy costs have a great impact on the consumption behaviours. This was shown at the beginning of Russia's invasion of Ukraine.

Innovation

Technological innovations, improvements in energy efficiency, and advances in policies and business models are essential to the success of the clean energy transition. They contribute to reducing the technology cost as well as the total cost of the transition itself, by providing competence and tools for making the right decisions while promoting implementation. The pace of European innovation and its barriers were brought to new attention in 2024, along with a set of actions that should be implemented to overtake competing nations [10]. As a response to this, the European Commission presented the Competitiveness Compass [11] and proposed to establish the European Competitiveness Fund [12], to increase competitiveness in defence and industry.

Geopolitical instability

There are developments in the political situations in European countries, with changes in political governance, a more strained economic system and pressure from the outside. This has moved climate change down on the priority list. The pressure from the outside includes failing belief in a rule-based society, the threat of war, insecurity about allies, tax-war and pressure on industry export, leaving Europe vulnerable to outside players interfering with the political systems in Europe. This pressure can unite Europe and lead us in the direction of the REPowerEU++ scenario or exhaust the European efforts and weaken the union.

Policy and regulation

The complex interdependencies inherent in climate as well as energy policy and regulation in the European Union and related countries present a significant challenge. Examples of this are the questioning of the European power market regulation, lack of instruments for EU to enforce implementation of national climate targets, and suboptimal measures to combat rising energy prices (e.g. fixed power price). We also see this problem globally, e.g. with the US withdrawal from the Paris Agreement in 2020 and 2026.

Results and findings

The developments outlined above suggest that several current trends in Europe increasingly resemble the conditions represented in the EU Trinity scenario: economic strain, slower innovation, geopolitical instability, and insufficient social and regulatory support for the clean energy transition. In that context, the ManOEUVRE computations show the consequences of allowing these trends to persist. They show that a divided Europe and

the geopolitical tensions outlined in the EU Trinity scenario will lead to a bleak outlook for the transition of the European energy system – and thus for achieving the climate goals. The EU Trinity scenario sees an increase in total energy system costs of 8% compared to e.g. the REPowerEU++ scenario, equivalent to over 2,873 billion Euros. At the same time, renewable energy capacities develop much slower than in REPowerEU++, with renewable electricity generation capacity at 990 GW compared to 1227 GW in 2030, and 1950 GW compared to 2178 GW in 2050. This also affects the deployment of flexibility in terms of hydrogen and storage deployment, which have a significantly faster uptake in the REPowerEU++ scenario compared to EU Trinity, where a hydrogen economy does not emerge (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Model results for installed energy storages (top) and transmission capacity (bottom).

Concerning electrification, EU Trinity shows a slower pace and efficiency progress compared to the other scenarios (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Model results for final energy consumption in TWh (area) and electrification of final energy in % (line) per sector.

While the electrification rate shows similar levels towards the end of the model horizon across all scenarios, in EU Trinity this is driven by fossil-based electricity generation for most of the period. This is particularly relevant considering the present European context. If investment in decarbonised capacity weakens, innovation slows down, and if political focus shifts away from climate action, electrification alone will not guarantee a successful clean energy transformation. Instead, the transition risks becoming more expensive and less effective. All in all, this outcome leads to a significantly higher emissions output, which is at close to 68 GtCO₂ in EU Trinity compared to just below 46 GtCO₂ in REPowerEU++. This means that the EU Trinity scenario is only barely aligned with a 2°C future, pointing to a high risk of not being able to successfully limit the rise to below 2°C compared to pre-industrial averages. Taking the environmental damage calculations of the German Environmental Agency, which calculated the negative effects of CO₂ on health and the environment between 345 and 990 € per ton of CO₂-eq., the substantially higher emissions in EU Trinity would imply significantly greater

societal and environmental costs [13]. Simultaneously, economic output in EU Trinity is reduced compared to more ambitious scenarios as strategic sectors important to Europe, such as renewable hydrogen, will not be realised. In the EU Trinity scenario, a hydrogen economy never manifests, and hydrogen consumption remains at around 2018 levels with an exclusive use in chemical processes and ammonia for fertilizer. To conclude, these findings show that the challenges currently emerging in Europe are not only short-term. If left unaddressed, they can fundamentally weaken the clean energy transition and reduce Europe's long-term welfare and resilience. ManOEUVRE therefore shows how crucial cross-national cooperation, regulatory support, faster innovation, and public acceptance are for a swift shift towards renewable energy sources to ensure that we turn the tide in Europe.

Recommendations

To increase the probability of steering Europe towards the more ambitious scenarios, we use the scenario assumptions and the results from the pan-European simulations to find measures that can be implemented.

- Support electrification, replacing domestic and industrial gas use, and fossil fuels in passenger and freight mobility.
- In parallel, develop regulatory frameworks to phase-out fossil fuel-based electricity generation without CCS.
- Develop regulatory frameworks for investments and operation of flexibility options across the energy system, including electricity and hydrogen storage, infrastructure, and demand-side flexibility.

- Improve the public attitude to and awareness of the transformation. Strategies for achieving this are outside of the scope of this project, but the results show that scenarios that manage this, provide a faster transition and a lower total cost of the energy system.

A resilient energy system in the European Union is less susceptible to influence from major global actors controlling critical technologies or resources. At the same time, a flexible and united Europe would be better positioned to negotiate better agreements with major global players. Last, but not least, reducing energy-related CO₂-emissions would limit the negative effects of climate-related events to society, the economy and the environment in Europe and around the world.

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